

Country Perspectives on Improving Technical Assistance in the Health Sector

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Extended data— Re-Imagining Technical Assistance project’s twenty principles of good technical assistance

1. Strengthen the system as a whole	2. Foster strong governance	3. Build upon the existing system	4. Cultivate trust
<p>1.1 Begin with a realistic plan To increase accountability and the effective use of resources, governments should lead the development of long-term strategic plans and coordinate the efforts of technical assistance (TA) providers. Governments and TA providers should regularly consult strategic and national health plans to ensure that TA interventions are aligned with the plans. Agreements with TA providers should incorporate input from the Ministry of Health and include realistic timelines (e.g., making work plans available in time to inform TA priorities, assignments, and schedules; extending work plans to allow more time for implementation and evaluation) and budgets (e.g., TA providers taking part in co-funding memoranda of understanding should ensure government commitments are responsible).</p>	<p>2.1 Ensure that the government is in the driver’s seat Governments should lead their country’s agendas and determine where, why, and how aid is distributed. TA providers should align with local priorities and be accountable to the government for the work they do. A more robust system of accountability between governments and TA providers would enable TA to contribute to and be evaluated in accordance with national strategic plans.</p>	<p>3.1 Develop budgets that reflect the realities on the ground Budgets need to be flexible enough to adjust to real-world situations. TA budgets often underestimate the cost variations in different locations and do not permit modifying line items in response to evolving needs. Prioritizing the engagement of local human and material resources supports the local economy and can often reduce costs. Surplus funding should be strategically invested to enhance the sustainability of essential vulnerable initiatives.</p>	<p>4.1 Create a collaborative environment Good TA requires establishing ongoing vertical and horizontal communication between the government and TA providers. Communication should center on collaboration, knowledge sharing, and supporting stakeholders to make informed decisions while considering relevant trade-offs and priorities. Enabling decision making at different levels is likely to improve task delegation and efficiency.</p>

<p>1.2 Adopt a comprehensive, multi-sectoral approach TA donors and providers should discontinue investing in vertical health areas and focus instead on strengthening the health system as a whole. This will require forging partnerships to develop an integrated, multisectoral approach to addressing challenges and distributing TA resources across arenas for longer periods of time. TA actors must avoid creating or using parallel vertical systems that duplicate existing systems or processes. Agreements and contracts should allow flexibility for TA interventions to shift focus in response to evolving needs.</p>	<p>2.2 Balance external expertise with local knowledge Identify and build on the knowledge of local experts so that interventions are contextually responsive and based on local needs.</p>	<p>3.2 Prioritize sustainability and longer-term thinking Country-based stakeholders should be identified and engaged from the outset with a clear plan for transitioning the work to the local government (national, state, or regional). The timeline of interventions should be determined in consultation with local authorities knowledgeable about the context and the time needed for a project to effect change. Transition plans for sustainability should be developed at the start of the project to secure buy-in from country stakeholders (e.g., via the commitment of resources like people, funds, and infrastructure to assume responsibility for the project when the TA provider leaves. This type of transition plan compels teams to develop realistic timelines and measures of success.</p>	<p>4.2 Emphasize learning through iteration: best practices and failures alike are informative An emphasis on learning releases TA providers from the pressure to report only positive outcomes and ignore negative ones, regardless of what can be learned. Communicating lessons learned can foster an environment of mutual support and facilitate more effective planning. In particular, failures that occur in pilot projects should be communicated to stakeholders, with the ultimate goal of gaining a better understanding of the enablers of and barriers to success and scale up.</p>
<p>1.3 Minimize funding gaps and duplicative efforts Standardizing funding processes and mechanisms and better aligning grants and awards cycles can help to minimize funding gaps and facilitate timely budget updates. TA funding should be used to fill gaps or expand existing</p>	<p>2.3 Build local capacity TA providers should actively include local experts in their projects (and perhaps be incentivized to do so). Providers should coordinate with local experts to identify the roles the experts should play and focus on building their skills as part of</p>	<p>3.3 Strengthen internal accountability mechanisms within countries Increasing accountability among all actors and investing in a country's internal accountability mechanisms will help to build a more reliable system for partners to invest in. To ensure that funds</p>	<p>4.3 Strengthen community feedback loops Beneficiaries of TA should clearly communicate their needs to TA donors and providers, sharing their opinions on intervention plans and providing ongoing feedback during project implementation to inform mid-course corrections. Information</p>

<p>successful approaches, as opposed to supporting multiple similar projects on one vertical. Data-sharing agreements and policies should contribute to reducing duplicative efforts.</p>	<p>long-term sustainability. Drawing on institutional memory, transferring knowledge, and building capacity are essential to reducing the knowledge and skills gaps that can emerge between private-sector TA providers and local government actors. Promoting training for public servants and local students seeking to enter the health sector are also crucial actions.</p>	<p>are not misappropriated, donors often tightly control how money is managed, relying and trusting in their own accountability systems over those of the state. These situations create an opaque environment where financial flows and information are not readily shared among the stakeholders engaged in TA. Strengthening government accountability mechanisms and institutions can lead to more autonomy managing funds. It can also encourage third parties to dispense funding at more peripheral levels for more efficient disbursement to beneficiaries.</p>	<p>about the project's progress should be routinely shared with beneficiaries to promote two-way transparency.</p>
<p>1.4 Ensure ongoing funding for core priorities The typical five-year TA project cycle leads to a disruption in health services when TA ends. Health systems require significant support to continue delivering services when TA projects come to a close. Thus, it is critical to engage local stakeholders in TA at the outset, focus TA services on long-term sustainability, and strengthen coordination across the components of the health system. Collaborating with community members representing key populations and local leaders to</p>	<p>2.4 Engage local stakeholders and avoid one-size-fits-all approaches TA providers should ensure that local stakeholders are involved in TA early and equipped to take over once TA funding expires. Providers should also ensure that the local perspective is well represented during planning and implementation and allocate time and resources to develop plans with local stakeholders and contextualize interventions with their input.</p>	<p>3.4 Invest in existing structures and work with local resources TA providers should ensure that local stakeholders have a supportive work environment and infrastructure. TA providers should function within existing structures and resources, even if it means sacrificing short-term gains. It is important to avoid reliance on processes, models, or resources that cannot be sustained once TA donors and providers are no longer present.</p>	<p>4.4 Build reciprocity in the evaluation TA should be evaluated according to the following criteria: the extent to which outcomes are met and were realistic, the degree to which the project benefits the zone of intervention (country, province, or state), and the quality of the TA delivered. Developing criteria for good TA will be essential, and collecting feedback from beneficiaries can help to measure the success of interventions.</p>

<p>agree on priorities and goals can facilitate longer-term financial support when there is a change in TA provider or local leadership. Developing rigorous transition plans for entering and exiting a country helps to reduce costs (e.g., transferring equipment and vehicles from one project to another instead of making new purchases).</p> <p>1.5 Standardize incentive structures to maximize impact It is critical to encourage long-term planning that emphasizes efficiency and sustainable outcomes. Striking a balance between incentives that motivate individuals' performance and collective incentives that focus on shared goals and reward teamwork is essential to long-term sustainability. Standardizing pay structures and per diems will also help to create equitable systems that do not foster competition with one another.</p>	<p>2.5 Follow local protocols and adjust cadence accordingly The time needed for TA plan review and approval by government stakeholders should be taken into account when developing project timelines. Every effort should be made to avoid circumventing the government, instead planning for its engagement throughout the life of the project. The provision of TA could become more efficient by aligning TA plans and timelines with those of government-led initiatives.</p>	<p>3.5 Transition away from dependence on donor funding TA providers should hold the state accountable for funding its health system, promoting self-sufficient programs to ensure financial sustainability at the national and local level.</p>	<p>4.5 Change the data culture Data collected about the project (including the project's initial monitoring, evaluation, and research plans) and evaluation findings should be shared with stakeholders to promote transparency, accountability, strategic decision making, and improved planning.</p>
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Sonder Collective. (2020). Re-imagining Technical Assistance: Global Design Principles, Nigeria and the Democratic Republic of Congo Case Study.

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